

GOUT AND ITS ASSOCIATION WITH GOUTY NEPHROPATHY: AN ANALYSIS OF 46 PATIENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14263759>

Introduction: Gout is a widespread metabolic disorder characterized by chronic hyperuricemia, which leads to the deposition of monosodium urate crystals in various tissues and joints. This accumulation results in acute inflammatory arthritis and, over time, can lead to severe complications, including gouty nephropathy. Gouty nephropathy is a pathological condition of the kidneys caused by prolonged exposure to elevated uric acid levels, leading to progressive renal-dysfunction.

This thesis examines the clinical and biochemical features of gout and its renal complications, focusing specifically on the levels of creatinine and uric acid in the serum of affected patients. By analyzing the data from 46 gout patients, this study identifies critical trends and risk factors associated with the progression of gout to nephropathy, especially among older individuals.

Materials and Methods

The study cohort consisted of 46 patients diagnosed with gout. Among these, 43 were males, and 3 were females, reflecting the higher prevalence of the disease in men. The age range of the participants was between 40 and 70 years, ensuring a focus on adult and older populations who are more likely to develop gout and its complications. Data collection included detailed demographic information, clinical presentations, and biochemical markers such as serum creatinine and uric acid levels. Patients were categorized into subgroups based on age (younger than 50 years and older than 50 years) and the presence or absence of gouty nephropathy.

Data: 1. Patients: 46 patients diagnosed with gout, including 3 females and 44 males.

2. Age Range: Patients are aged between 40 and 70 years.

3. Gouty Nephropathy: 20 male patients were diagnosed with gouty nephropathy, with 15 of them being older than 50.

4. Biochemical Analysis Results: Creatinine Levels: 20 patients had creatinine levels above 130 mmol/l (normal creatinine levels for men are 62-106 mmol/l, and for women, 53-97 mmol/l).

Uric Acid Levels: All patients had elevated uric acid levels, confirming the diagnosis of gout.

Older Patients (Above 50 years): Among those over 50 years old, creatinine levels were higher, exceeding 130 mmol/l, and uric acid levels were above 7 mg/dl (normal uric acid levels for men are 3.5-7.2 mg/dl, and for women, 2.6-6.0 mg/dl).

Analysis: Creatinine Levels: Elevated creatinine levels indicate impaired kidney function. The higher creatinine levels in patients over 50 suggest a greater risk of developing gouty nephropathy. Monitoring creatinine is crucial in assessing kidney damage in gout patients.

Uric Acid Levels: Elevated uric acid is characteristic of gout and is linked to the formation of uric acid crystals in the kidneys and joints. The higher levels of uric acid in patients over 50 indicate a more severe progression of gout and an increased risk of nephropathy.

Clinical Implications: The correlation between age and biochemical markers shows that gout and its complications, such as gouty nephropathy, are more prevalent in older individuals, and these patients require careful monitoring and management.

Conclusion: Elevated creatinine and uric acid levels are significant biochemical markers in the diagnosis and progression of gout and gouty nephropathy. Patients over the age of 50 are at higher risk of developing kidney complications, making it essential to monitor these markers regularly and initiate early treatment to prevent further damage.

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